

Emergence of Oropouche fever in Latin America: a narrative review

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Since its discovery in 1955, the incidence and geographical spread of reported Oropouche virus (OROV) infections have increased. Oropouche fever has been suggested to be one of the most important vector-borne diseases in Latin America. However, both literature on OROV and genomic sequence availability are scarce, with few contributing laboratories worldwide. Three reassortant OROV glycoprotein gene variants termed Iquitos, Madre de Dios, and Perdões virus have been described from humans and non-human primates. OROV predominantly causes acute febrile illness, but severe neurological disease such as meningoencephalitis can occur. Due to unspecific symptoms, laboratory diagnostics are crucial. Several laboratory tests have been developed but robust commercial tests are hardly available. Although OROV is mainly transmitted by biting midges, it has also been detected in several mosquito species and a wide range of vertebrate hosts, which likely facilitates its widespread emergence. However, potential non-human vertebrate reservoirs have not been systematically studied. Robust animal models to investigate pathogenesis and immune responses are not available. Epidemiology, pathogenesis, transmission cycle, cross-protection from infections with OROV reassortants, and the natural history of infection remain unclear. This Review identifies Oropouche fever as a neglected disease and offers recommendations to address existing knowledge gaps, enable risk assessments, and ensure effective public health responses.

Key messages

- Over the past 70 years, a notable increase in the incidence and geographical spread of reported Oropouche virus (OROV) infections has been observed, highlighting a growing public health concern.
- The OROV genome is tri-segmented, which allows for reassortment. Three OROV reassortants are known, among which Madre de Dios and Iquitos viruses have been associated with human diseases.
- Human OROV infection occurs through the bites of midges, but its presence in various mosquito species and a wide range of vertebrate hosts contributes to the potential for widespread emergence of OROV. However, the virus' transmission cycle is poorly understood.
- OROV causes febrile symptoms indistinguishable from common pathogens endemic to the Americas. Occasionally OROV infection can result in severe conditions, such as meningoencephalitis.
- Due to the virus' unspecific symptoms, laboratory diagnostics are crucial. Several in-house molecular and serological tests have been developed, but robust commercial tests are scarcely available.
- Animal models of OROV infection are restricted to rodent models. The pathogenesis of OROV and its reassortants is poorly understood. The possibility and extent of repeated infection by different OROV glycoprotein reassortants are unknown.
- The gaps in understanding the epidemiology, ecology, and pathogenesis of OROV, including its reassortants, are substantial. Addressing these knowledge gaps is crucial for developing risk assessments and effective public health strategies to combat Oropouche fever, a prototypical neglected disease.

Introduction

Vector-borne diseases cause up to 28.8% of all emerging infectious diseases.¹ Arthropod-borne viruses (ie, arboviruses) comprise 39% of all pathogenic viruses discovered in humans between 1897 and 2010, and are a main cause of vector-borne diseases.^{2,3} The importance of arboviruses is best illustrated by the dengue virus (DENV), which is the most important arbovirus infecting over 100 000 000 humans annually.⁴ In contrast to vector-borne parasites, the global burden of arboviruses increased between 2007 and 2017.³ The true burden of arboviral disease is probably still underestimated.^{5,6} Poor knowledge of transmission cycles, non-specific clinical presentations, and scarcity of robust diagnostic tools are among the main problems that make arboviral infections and their effect on patient and public health difficult to identify.⁷

Latin America is considered a hot spot of emerging arboviruses due to its large biodiversity including relevant vertebrate reservoirs such as bats, rodents, and primates, and multiple invertebrate taxa.^{8,9} Moreover, key emergence factors are present in the region, comprising (1) ecological and socioeconomic factors, especially rapid population growth and often arbitrary urbanisation; (2) favourable climatic conditions for vector establishment and proliferation, and large diversity of ecosystems; and (3) intense human migration and major changes in land use, such as deforestation, illegal mining, and intensification of agriculture.^{5,10,11} Along with increased global connectivity, the Americas have therefore seen the emergence (and re-emergence) of several arboviruses, such as DENV, chikungunya virus (CHIKV), West Nile virus, and Zika virus (ZIKV), during the past 50 years. Nonetheless, only DENV and CHIKV are officially listed as pathogens causing a neglected tropical disease (NTD) by WHO.¹² However, the Pan American Health Organization has begun to acknowledge additional arboviruses as emergent and has started issuing guidelines for their diagnosis, treatment, and laboratory detection in the region.^{13,14}

The Pan American Health Organization considers DENV to be the biggest threat in the Americas because of its four serotypes and its well established urban transmission cycle.¹⁵ In addition, since their emergence on the American continent in 2013, CHIKV and ZIKV have caused millions of infections in the region, incurring approximately 140 000 disability-adjusted life-years every year and, in the case of ZIKV, congenital malformations.¹⁶⁻²⁰ Other arboviruses, such as Oropouche virus (OROV), Mayaro virus,²¹ or Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus,^{22,23} are also considered emergent in the region. Before the recent emergence of CHIKV and ZIKV from 2013 onwards, OROV was claimed to be the second most frequent arbovirus in Brazil after DENV, allegedly accounting for more than half a million estimated cases in Central and South America since its first identification.^{24,25}

Upon closer examination of OROV cases, estimates of its relevance have relied on a few small-scale studies;²⁶⁻²⁸ therefore, the true burden of OROV-induced disease remains unknown. Although Oropouche fever could be a prototypic NTD, incurring considerable health burden in affected countries, knowledge of OROV and the disease it causes is scarce.

This Review discusses the current state of research on OROV and identifies research gaps requiring further investigation to enhance patient care, enable risk assessments, and ensure effective public health responses to Oropouche fever.

Genetic features of OROV and its reassortants

OROV's genomic sequence availability

OROV belongs to the Simbu serogroup of the viral genus *Orthobunyavirus* in the Peribunyaviridae family. The OROV genome consists of three single-stranded, negative-sense RNA molecules: small (S), medium (M), and large (L) segment. The S segment encodes the nucleocapsid and a non-structural protein (NSs) in overlapping open reading frames; the M segment encodes the two glycoproteins Gc

and Gn, and a non-structural protein (NSm); and the L segment encodes the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (figure 1A).²⁹⁻³¹

513 sequences, including 50 sequences of OROV reassortants, were retrieved from GenBank. Most of those sequences corresponded to the S segment (n=256); this could be because this segment is the most conserved and the target of most PCR systems (compared with 142 M-derived sequences and 115 L-derived sequences), which restricts our knowledge and analysis of those genomic segments (figure 1B). This small number of sequences probably represents only a fraction of the existing OROV genetic diversity that is additionally biased towards few sampling sites and dates.

OROV reassortants

OROV's tri-segmented genome is susceptible to reassortment when two viruses co-infect a single cell, resulting in progeny with mixed genomic segments.³⁰⁻³² These events are important drivers of genetic divergence, potentially altering vector competence and disease severity and therefore facilitating viral emergence.^{31,32} Among orthobunyaviruses circulating in South America, such as Fort Sherman virus and Jatobal virus, reassortment events are frequent.^{30,33} Because arboviral surveillance in the Americas is scarce, the number of OROV reassortants is possibly underestimated.^{30,34} Furthermore, experimental evidence shows possible reassortment between OROV and non-American orthobunyaviruses, such as Schmallenberg, Bunyamwera, and Oya viruses,³² underscoring the risk of new OROV reassortants emerging in the future.

Three OROV reassortants termed Iquitos virus (IQTV), Madre de Dios virus (MDDV), and Perdões virus (PDEV) have been identified. These reassortants contain the S and L segments of OROV, the M segment of unknown viruses, and, in the case of IQTV, an MDDV-related M segment, as highlighted by the high sequence distances of the reassortant M segments as compared with OROV (figure 2A) and the common ancestor of MDDV and IQTV in an M-based phylogenetic tree (figure 2B).^{29,34,37,38,39} The M segment's genetic diversity could be influenced by evolutionary pressure on the glycoproteins targeted by antibody-mediated immune response²⁹ and suggests that M segment-based reassortment could provide evolutionary benefits for evading population-level immunity, whereas S and L segments could be functionally linked due to the interaction of derived proteins during replication.^{29,40}

Data concerning the serological relationship between OROV and its reassortants, including IQTV, are scarce. Experiments have shown that mouse antisera against IQTV only weakly neutralise OROV, indicating distinct serotypes, with no reciprocal effect observed.³⁸ IQTV infection in two Peruvian patients triggered an increase in potentially pre-existing OROV immune responses, suggesting conserved epitopes but insufficient cross-protection.³⁸ The potential absence of cross-protection coupled with shared antigenicity among reassortants could result in antibody-dependent enhancement (ADE), a process that likely contributes to severe secondary DENV infections.⁴¹ Therefore, as OROV and its reassortants coexist, investigating their serological relationship is crucial to gauge potential ADE risks and any limitations in cross-protection.⁴¹

Bibliographic analysis of publications on OROV

Literature on OROV is scarce. Only 192 peer-reviewed papers published since July 1, 1961, to June 30, 2023, were retrieved from PubMed, highlighting the sparse research interest in OROV (figure 3A). We also conducted a Boolean search on the Web of Science on March 31, 2023, using the terms: "OROV" OR "virus del oropouche" OR "Oropouche virus" OR "Oropouche" OR "Oropouche" OR "Iquitos virus" OR "Madre de Dios virus" OR "Perdoes virus" (Title), OR "OROV" OR "Virus del oropouche" OR "Oropouche virus" OR "Oropouche" OR "Oropouche" OR "Iquitos virus" OR "Madre de Dios virus" OR "Perdoes virus" (Abstract), AND NOT poecilla OR guppy (Abstract) AND NOT trinidad (Abstract).

The search revealed that OROV research is conducted by a small number of groups; the top five authors contributed 67 articles, which represent 35% of all the articles on the subject. Further breakdown of these data indicates that most of these articles come from Brazil (57%) and the USA (38%). Bibliographic analysis of OROV literature showed high bibliographic coupling (two given works sharing a common reference) for articles published in the past decade (figure 3B). High bibliographic coupling can be explained by the low numbers of publications and little heterogeneity in literature, with the few researchers working on OROV citing the same papers because of insufficient new evidence.

Geographical distribution of OROV and its reassortants

Since its initial detection in 1955 in Trinidad and Tobago,⁴² OROV has been detected across Central and South America, spanning 5000 km south and 2000 km west, and its incidence has increased over the past several decades (figure 4). As of June, 2023, reports of OROV in human and non-human hosts have emerged pre-dominantly from rural and forest areas in Brazil,^{26,28,29,44-65} Peru,⁶⁶⁻⁷³ Ecuador,^{74,75,76,77} Argentina,⁴³ Bolivia,⁷⁴ Panama,²⁶ Colombia,⁷⁸⁻⁸⁰ and Venezuela.³⁷ The virus' first Caribbean detection—after its initial discovery in Trinidad and Tobago in 1955—occurred in Haiti in 2014,⁸¹ followed by a 2016 outbreak in non-endemic coastal regions of Ecuador and Peru^{76,82} and its emergence in a densely populated urban zone in northeastern Brazil.⁶³ In 2020, nearly half of a small rainforest village in French Guiana experienced a dengue-like syndrome, with OROV diagnosed in 43% (41/95) of inhabitants, suggesting OROV can present with high attack rates.⁸³ Colombian data from 2019 to 2021 attribute 11% (87/791) of acute febrile disease during this time period to OROV, with 16% (92/568) of Colombian patients testing positive for OROV IgG antibodies in chemiluminescent immunoassays.⁸⁴ Altogether, the available literature suggests a wide geographical expansion of OROV. IQTV was first isolated in 1999 from a patient in Iquitos, Peru, and has caused at least 160 human cases between 2005 and 2006.³⁸ In 2006, 15.4% (160/1037) of patients with undifferentiated febrile illness from Iquitos showed IQTV neutralising antibodies in plaque reduction neutralisation tests, which is slightly higher than the 14.9% (154/1037) found for OROV. Additionally, 3.4% (35/1037) had antibodies to both viruses, suggesting cocirculation or substantial cross-neutralisation.³⁸ MDDV was identified in a febrile patient in Peru³⁹ in 2007, and in a white-faced capuchin monkey in Venezuela in 2010, nearly 2000 km away.³⁷ PDEV has only been isolated once in 2012, from two black-tufted marmosets in Minas Gerais, Brazil.²⁹

Clinical presentation, treatment, and vaccine

Most information available on the clinical presentation of the infection with OROV and its reassortants stems from case reports or small-scale outbreaks. Therefore, the evidence available on clinical presentation and sequelae is poor, and morbidity and mortality could be underestimated.

Oropouche fever is generally mild and self-limiting and often begins with a 3–10-day incubation period,^{44,62} after which patients develop a febrile illness with headache, arthralgia, myalgia, nausea, vomiting, chills, and photophobia.^{72,82,83,85} Some patients have less common symptoms, such as rash, retro-orbital pain, anorexia, and haemorrhagic manifestations.^{44,72,82} Severe clinical presentations, which are rare, could involve CNS infections that result in aseptic meningitis or meningoencephalitis.^{57,62,64,83,86,87} The disease is typically biphasic, with an acute phase lasting 2–4 days, followed by a remission and a resurgence of symptoms 7–10 days after onset.^{64,83} Most patients recover without sequelae, although persistent myalgia and asthenia lasting up to 1 month have been reported.⁸³ No deaths have been attributed to OROV infection yet. Similarly to OROV, IQTV infection presents with fever, headache, eye pain, body pain, arthralgia, diarrhoea, and chills.³⁸ MDDV was reported to cause undifferentiated febrile illness, and no human infection has been recorded for

PDEV.^{29,39} The rate of asymptomatic infections is difficult to estimate as studies generally include febrile patients; a single study reported symptoms in up to 63% of patients with OROV infection.⁶⁵

Co-infections of OROV with reassortants have not been reported. However, acute infections of OROV and other arboviruses can occur, as observed in Peru and Colombia with DENV.^{72,73,84} Co-infections of OROV–ZIKV and OROV–CHIKV have been described at low detection rates,⁷² as well as a triple co-infection of OROV–DENV–CHIKV identified once in western Brazil,⁸⁶ but the effect of co-infections by OROV and other co-circulating arboviruses on disease severity remains unclear.

Currently, no specific antiviral treatment against OROV infection is available. Ribavirin, a broad-spectrum antiviral, was ineffective against OROV in vivo in mice;⁸⁸ mycophenolic acid, which has shown in vitro activity against yellow fever virus, DENV, and Semliki Forest virus, was also ineffective against OROV.^{89,90} Interferon alfa can restrict viral replication in vitro and in vivo in mice when administered early or pre-infection, but its clinical relevance is unclear.⁹¹

Although no vaccine is currently available for OROV, a single study⁸⁸ presented a candidate vaccine based on a replication-competent chimeric vesicular stomatitis virus expressing complete or truncated OROV glycoproteins, which showed a reduction in viral loads and symptom severity in mice; moreover, another study predicted novel epitope candidates for epitope-based peptide vaccine design against OROV using computational methods.⁹² Other orthobunyavirus vaccines could guide the development of OROV vaccines. A chemically inactivated Schmallenberg virus (SBV) vaccine is licensed for veterinary use in the EU,⁹³ and an SBV nucleoprotein fragment-based vaccine has been shown to reduce viraemia in infected mice.⁹⁴ Evidence regarding vaccine-induced cross-protection in the Simbu serogroup is scarce. A trivalent vaccine comprising two inactivated Simbu serogroup viruses, Akabane virus (AKAV) and Aino virus (AINOV), failed to prevent SBV infection in cows.⁹⁵

Laboratory diagnosis

Identifying the causative agent of acute febrile illness without laboratory tests is hardly feasible and sometimes inaccurate. Therefore, many treatable diseases with non-specific symptoms are misdiagnosed as dengue or malaria.^{7,96} Similarly, discrimination between OROV and other pathogens causing acute febrile illness based solely on clinical symptoms was shown to be unreliable.⁷³ Consequently, patients are being misdiagnosed or untreated and outbreaks could remain unrecognised. To verify acute OROV infections, laboratories typically employ three primary diagnostic criteria: a positive PCR result, the identification of specific IgM, or the detection of seroconversion through paired samples. Historically, serological methods were predominant but have been gradually replaced by molecular methods.^{24,27,40,85,97}

Molecular diagnosis

Molecular detection of OROV is typically possible during the first week on acute-phase specimens.^{24,40,61,85,98} Real-time RT-PCR in sera collected during the first 5 days of illness has shown a 93% detection rate.⁹⁸ Serum viral loads can range from 10⁴ to 10⁸ genome copies per mL,⁹⁸ and the presence of low viraemia in recent cases highlights the need for sensitive PCR assays.⁸⁴ Real-time RT-PCR is preferred for early-stage diagnosis due to its speed, ease, and reduced contamination risk. Various in-house tests have been developed,^{51,61,77,84,98,99,100} including multiplexed formats for detecting co-circulating Mayaro virus.¹⁰¹ Most assays target the OROV S segment,^{77,98,100,101} which does not distinguish between OROV and its reassortants. Typing can be enabled by including M segment-based primers.^{61,84,102} Conventional RT-PCR is widely used for research^{51,61,77,98,99,100,102} alongside virus isolation.^{76,79,83}

Serum or plasma are the preferred samples for OROV diagnosis.^{51,54,72,79,83,84} In patients with OROV infections involving the

CNS, viral RNA detection, viral isolation from cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), and IgM detection in CSF have been reported.^{57,62,64} Furthermore, OROV has been detected by PCR in saliva and urine collected from symptomatic patients within 5 days of disease onset,^{61,63} suggesting that these samples could serve as alternative specimens for OROV detection during the acute phase of infection. Additionally, although impractical for individual patient testing due to high cost and reduced sensitivity, metagenomic sequencing could serve as an additional environmental surveillance tool. Pooled vector-derived or patient-derived samples can provide genetic information of circulating virus strains. The use of samples from wastewater has also been explored for flaviviruses,¹⁰³ but further exploratory analysis is needed to assess whether this approach can be employed for other arboviruses, especially OROV. Further implementation of these methods will help to clarify OROV genetic diversity, enabling the improvement of diagnostic assays, vaccines, and antivirals.^{103,104}

Serological diagnosis

After acute infection, molecular testing should be supplemented by serological methods. Immune responses against OROV are not well studied, but serological procedures can detect OROV-specific IgM and IgG in serum, plasma, and CSF.^{24,40,56,59,64,67,71,84,85} Ideally, IgM testing in CSF should be done together with IgM testing in paired serum samples and supported by assessments of blood-brain barrier leakage to confirm intrathecal immunoglobulin synthesis.¹⁰⁵ Existing in-house serological tools include enzyme immunoassays, neutralisation tests, complement fixation tests, immunofluorescence tests, and haemagglutination inhibition tests.^{74,75,28,42,45,48,70,106} Tests based on the nucleocapsid (N) protein, which elicits a strong humoral immune response, have been developed,^{84,107,108} however, these tests show cross-reactivity due to the conservation of epitopes on N proteins among many Simbu serogroup viruses.¹⁰⁷⁻¹¹⁰ Although commercial Gc or N antigens are not available for OROV, robust commercial immunoassays are hardly available. Neutralisation tests are considered the gold standard for arbovirus serology,¹³ but they are not often used for patient diagnosis due to long turnaround times and the need for handling infectious viruses under biosafety level 3 conditions.

Robustness of laboratory diagnosis in articles reporting infection with OROV and its reassortants

55 articles published between 1960 and 2022 indicate a shift in diagnostic tools used for OROV and reassortant infections (figure 5). Before the 2010s, serological methods were commonly used, particularly in retrospective studies.^{28,45-50,53,68,70,106} However, in the past 15 years, the use of robust techniques (eg, RT-PCR and sequencing) has greatly enhanced the accuracy of detecting OROV infections and differentiating them from their reassortants.^{29,38,39,44,57,60-64,66,67,72,76,79,81-83,86} Nonetheless, OROV and its reassortants are most probably still underdiagnosed or misdiagnosed due to symptoms resembling those of classical arboviral diseases reported in Central and South America, highlighting the need for effective differential laboratory testing.⁷²

Transmission cycles of OROV

Understanding the arboviral transmission cycle allows for the identification of geographical areas and people at risk for infection. OROV is probably maintained through a sylvatic and an urban cycle (appendix p 1). The biting midge *Culicoides paraensis* is considered the main OROV vector because of viral isolation during outbreaks and vector competence observed in vivo under laboratory conditions.^{46,47-49,65,111} Humans are the suspected link between the sylvatic and urban transmission cycles given that *C paraensis* is present in both urban and rural settings.⁴⁰ Some OROV outbreaks have also coincided with human-driven environmental changes, such as deforestation, increased agriculture, and infrastructure development.^{69,82,83,112} These changes

can alter vector distribution and increase contacts among vectors, vertebrate reservoirs, and humans.¹¹³

Humans are the major vertebrate hosts in the urban cycle of OROV.^{38,68,71} Whether urban OROV transmission is transient, introduced via human movements, or permanent but at low levels and therefore undetected is unclear, and the potential role of domestic animals as amplifying hosts requires further investigation.^{34,46,102,114} The sylvatic cycle is less understood than the urban cycle, with definitive reservoirs and amplifying hosts yet to be identified. OROV antibodies have been found in wild birds, sloths, non-human primates, and rodents,^{46,47,78,115,116,117} alongside sporadic isolations from sloths and non-human primates in Brazil.^{45,53,102} Systematic studies of OROV non-human reservoir hosts are scarce.

The detection of OROV in a coastal region of Ecuador where *C paraensis* is absent (or yet to be found¹¹⁸) suggests the possibility of other vectors involved in OROV transmission.⁷⁶ Minor mutations can enhance vector-borne transmission, as evidenced by CHIKV adaption to *Aedes albopictus*.¹¹⁹ *Culex quinquefasciatus*, a primary and widespread vector of West Nile virus,⁵ was suspected to be involved in OROV transmissions in Brazil and French Guiana.^{44,83,120}

Conversely, low efficiency in viral transmission has been observed experimentally for *C quinquefasciatus*.¹²¹⁻¹²³ The main DENV vectors, *Aedes aegypti* and *A albopictus*, have been found to be ineffective OROV vectors,¹²¹ whereas other mosquitoes belonging to the species *Couillettidia venezuelensis*,⁴² *Aedes serratus*,^{42,45,124} *Psorophora cingulata*, and *Haemagogus tropicalis* were found to be naturally infected by OROV.¹²⁴ However, vector competence studies for these mosquito species are missing. If confirmed, this wide vector range would be only comparable with few other clinically relevant arboviruses, such as Japanese Encephalitis virus and Rift Valley fever virus.⁵ Although OROV dissemination seems restricted to South and Central American regions, both primary and supposed secondary vectors are not,^{122,125} highlighting the risk of further dissemination and emergence in other parts of the world. A study estimated that 2-5 million people were at direct risk of exposure to OROV in regions up to the southern USA.¹²⁶

Animal models

To date, hamster and mouse models have been described for OROV infection but not for reassortants. In immunocompetent Syrian golden hamster models, OROV causes systemic disease analogous to humans, as well as liver injury and severe neurological symptoms, such as motor deficits and paralysis.^{127,128} In immuno-competent mice, OROV infection outcomes range from no clinical signs, to few,^{88,129-131} and to low mortality rates.¹³² OROV infection in mice lacking the receptor for type I interferon (IFN) induces increased mortality rates and caused extensive liver and spleen damage.^{129,130} Suckling mice develop severe neurological symptoms before death with no observed hepatotropism.^{89,91,133,134} OROV hepatotropism has been observed in naturally infected non-human primates, with OROV and PDEV isolated from marmosets,^{29,135} but non-human primate models that better characterise infection by OROV and reassortants have not yet been developed.

Pathogenesis

OROV infection elicits varied cellular and systemic responses, involving multiple host factors. Peripheral blood mononuclear cells are supposed initial targets of OROV, but their virus replication capacity is relatively small.¹³⁶ Plasmacytoid dendritic cells important for type I IFN and proinflammatory cytokines production, are also probable targets.¹³⁰

A key aspect of OROV immune evasion is its NSs protein, which antagonises IFN and could induce apoptosis as observed in other pathogenic orthobunyaviruses, sidestepping immune responses.^{137,138} Additionally, microRNAs miR-217 and miR-576-3p increase during infection, which potentially inhibits the antiviral IFN beta response.¹³⁹

For cellular entry, lipoprotein-related protein 1 is a key host factor aiding OROV entry, as it is also for Rift Valley fever virus, highlighting its role in bunyavirus infections.¹⁴⁰

In severe cases, OROV can affect the CNS; however, the exact infiltration mechanism remains unclear. An *in vivo* mouse study indicated blood–brain barrier leakage and a possible neural pathway for initial CNS invasion.¹³⁴ OROV disrupts IFN responses in human primary astrocytes *in vitro*, potentially leading to neuropathology.¹⁴¹ However, *ex vivo* studies in adult human brains found no OROV-infected astrocytes, whereas microglia were more commonly infected.¹⁴²

Gaps of knowledge and recommendations

Genetics and reassortants

No instances of OROV reinfection have been recorded, and examining the serological relationship between OROV and its reassortants remains crucial. Similarly, the impact of reassortment on OROV host range and pathogenesis remains unknown. We recommend that *in vitro* investigations are conducted to explore the potential for reassortment between OROV and other American orthobunyaviruses. Furthermore, orthobunyavirus surveillance capabilities should be enhanced to distinguish and probe for reassortant viruses.

Disease surveillance and epidemiology

OROV surveillance is suboptimal, with incomplete diagnostic panel inclusion of the virus and its reassortants. Clinical understanding is based on minor outbreaks or isolated cases, necessitating longitudinal studies to describe asymptomatic infection and define clinical presentation and potential long-lasting sequelae. The correlation of specific symptoms or their severity with OROV and reassortant infection also requires further investigation. Existing seroprevalence studies are scarce. Consequently, reliable data to estimate the true extent of OROV circulation or to distinguish it from its reassortants are currently lacking. We recommend that comprehensive longitudinal studies and cross-sectional seroprevalence studies are implemented to improve understanding of eventual long-lasting or chronic effects of OROV fever, and to monitor the circulation of OROV and its reassortants to assess the potential for reinfection or multiple infections by different OROV reassortants. Metagenomics combined with vector or patient pool-based analyses can improve genomic surveillance and allow investigation of co-infections and vectors. The potential of wastewater surveillance for the detection and monitoring of OROV and other circulating arboviruses should also be explored.

Entomological and environmental surveillance

Despite isolating OROV from various species, the role of mosquitoes in transmission cycles remains unclear.¹²¹ Should OROV better adapt to the prevalent vectors *A. aegypti* and *A. albopictus*, its geographical spread could be substantially widened and, in regions where OROV is already present, infections could increase.¹¹⁹ The role of *C. quinquefasciatus*, given its wide geographical spread, needs clarification.¹²⁰ More vector competence studies are therefore necessary. Furthermore, information on OROV's transmission cycle is either outdated or incomplete. Virus isolation from reservoirs has been sporadic; only a handful of articles report isolation of OROV^{53,135} or reassortants^{37,135} from non-human hosts. Additionally, the dissemination of these hosts does not completely coincide with regions reporting OROV outbreaks. For example, the sloth and capuchin species, from which OROV and MDDV have been isolated, are native solely to northwestern South America^{143,144}—far below the geographical range of described OROV infections. Surveillance of sylvatic reservoirs and emergence events needs to be increased, and the potential for long-distance OROV dissemination (eg, by migratory birds) requires investigation. We recommend that currently known sylvatic reservoirs are confirmed and that further reservoirs and amplifying hosts are identified, especially in regions with outbreaks

within the past decade or in regions with an apparent absence of known reservoirs.

Detection tools

The evaluation of OROV diagnostics remains difficult due to the absence of reference material, external quality assessments, and comparative studies. Information about viral loads and immune response kinetics in various body fluids stems only from isolated cases. Longitudinal studies are essential to identify optimal specimens for diagnosis and standardise sampling for diagnostics and research. Additionally, exploring potential correlations between prolonged viraemia or high viral loads and disease severity, akin to other arboviruses, could be valuable.¹⁴⁵ Current molecular and serological assays often struggle to differentiate between OROV and its reassortants, and commercial tests are mostly unavailable. Laboratory diagnostics of OROV should therefore be improved. The development of point-of-care rapid diagnostic tools could help implement OROV diagnostics on a larger scale, especially in rural areas. Pathogenesis, animal models, and cross-protection OROV pathogenesis is poorly understood, and factors leading to severe disease remain to be identified. Reverse genetics systems developed for OROV could be exploited for this purpose.^{137,146} Animal models are restricted to rodents, but the development of adequate animal models will be essential for OROV pathogenesis and vaccine research, including assessments of potential ADE. Safe human challenge models have proven to be valuable for DENV research and could be explored for OROV in the future.¹⁴⁷ The amino acid divergence in the M segment between OROV and IQTV or MDDV resembles that of other Simbu serogroup viruses, for which an experimental vaccine failed to afford cross-protection. The available genomic and serological data for OROV and its reassortants suggest that development of vaccines against Oropouche fever could be challenging. We recommend that animal models for OROV and reassortants are expanded, that the cross-protection potential of existing vaccines be explored for OROV, and that the development of an effective, safe, stable, and affordable OROV vaccine is prioritised.

Conclusion

OROV has the potential to emerge as a substantial threat given its wide host and vector range, diverse environmental spread, potential for severe course of disease, and existence of human-infecting reassortants that could correspond to different serotypes. Despite the promising increase in research, knowledge of the virus lags compared with other American arboviruses. Intensifying international collaboration, including between Latin American countries in which OROV is endemic, and funding to bridge these knowledge gaps is imperative, as this will simultaneously enhance our understanding of other neglected diseases and inform public health policies. Therefore, OROV represents a prototypic NTD that necessitates investigation to assess and minimise its health burden.

Contributors

KMW, IP-H, and LP contributed to the literature search, figure conceptualisation and realisation, and writing of the original draft. EFdO-F and CF contributed to figure conceptualisation and data analysis. XdL contributed to the study design. JFD contributed to the study design and editing and writing of the final draft. All authors were involved in reviewing the manuscript.

Declaration of interests

We declare no competing interests.

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Figure 1: OROV structure and genomic sequence availability

(A) OROV structure and genomic organisation. (B) Nucleotide sequences available on GenBank for each segment up to June, 2023. A total of 15 sequences (segments: small [S], n=11; medium [M], n=2; and large [L], n=2) labelled “unverified” on GenBank (ie, GenBank staff could not verify the accuracy of the submitted sequences) were excluded. For S and L segments, sequences from OROV and reassortants are merged; for the M segment, sequences from OROV and reassortants are represented separately. Information on the genomic sequences used for figure 1B is available in the appendix. IQTV=Iquitos virus. MDDV=Madre de Dios virus. NSm=non-structural protein M. NSs=non-structural protein S. OROV=Oropouche virus. PDEV=Perdões virus. RdRp=RNA-dependent RNA polymerase. UTR=untranslated region. Figure created with BioRender.com (A) and R ggplot2 package (B).

Figure 2: Evolutionary characteristics of OROV and genetically related viruses

(A) Maximum amino acid sequence distance between OROV, selected members of the Simbu serogroup, and BUNV belonging to a different serogroup. Sequences were aligned using MAFFT (<https://mafft.cbrc.jp/>; algorithm: auto; scoring matrix BLOSUM62) with all available complete genomic sequences of OROV, IQTV, MDDV, and PDEV, and to the reference sequences of FPV, JATV, MANV, SBV, SIMV, and UTIV. These viruses were selected to improve visualisation of the genetic diversity between OROV and its reassortants by comparing the distance within Simbu and between Simbu and Bunyamwera serogroups. The amino acid p-distance matrix was generated using MEGA X (www.megasoftware.net) using a pairwise deletion option. JATV, originally considered an OROV reassortant,³⁵ is now classified as a separate species by the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses.³⁶ Sequences labelled “unverified” in GenBank (ie, GenBank staff could not verify the accuracy of the submitted sequences) were excluded. All sequences were retrieved from GenBank in June, 2023. (B) Maximum likelihood phylogenetic trees done in MEGA (MEGA X) using a Whelan and Goldman substitution model and complete deletion option based on translated coding sequences of the L, M, and S segments. Black circles at nodes represent support values of at least 0.70 from 1000 bootstrap replicates. OROV sequences were selected to cover the variability of the three genome segments and all available sequences of the reassortant viruses. Information on the genomic sequences used for figure 2A and 2B is available in the appendix. OROV=Oropouche virus. L=large segment. M=medium segment. S=small segment. IQTV=Iquitos virus. MDDV=Madre de Dios virus. PDEV=Perdões virus. JATV=Jatobal virus. UTIV=Utinga virus. FPV=Facey’s Paddock virus. MANV=Manzanilla virus. SBV=Schmallenberg virus. SIMV=Simbu virus. BUNV=Bunyamwera virus. AUS=Australia. BRA=Brazil. ECU=Ecuador. NLD=Netherlands. PER=Peru. TTO=Trinidad and Tobago. VEN=Venezuela. ZAF=South Africa.

Figure 3: Literature on Oropouche virus (OROV) and its reassortants

(A) The number of publications in PubMed on OROV and reassortants up to June 30, 2023. (B) Bibliographic coupling in OROV literature from a Web of Science search (accessed March 31, 2023). Each node represents a publication (indicated with name of the first author and year of publication); connected nodes represent articles sharing at least 15 references. Nodes are distributed in two dimensions by the number of references shared; clustered nodes therefore represent similar publications. Node size represents the total link strength of the node (ie, the sum of all link scores from each publication pair). The bigger the node, the higher the bibliographic coupling with the rest of the reference set. Colour scale represents the year of publication. Figure created with RStudio (A) and VOSviewer (B; University of Leiden, 2010).

Figure 4: Oropouche virus detections in humans, other vertebrate hosts, midges, and mosquitoes

Confirmed cases were detected with sequencing or RT-PCR or neutralisation tests or viral isolation and complement fixation test or seroconversion in paired samples with any type of serological tool. Probable infections were detected with ELISA, immunofluorescence tests, or haemagglutination inhibition tests in non-paired samples. Estimated cases were taken from the literature without laboratory evidence. Cases from Argentina in 2000–09, included in the map, were reported as personal communication in a textbook of paediatric infectious diseases⁴³ and not in a peer-reviewed article. Host and vector cases detected with any method were included. Maps were created with QGIS (<https://qgis.org/en/site/>; long-term release version 3.22 Białowieża) on a regional level and by decade. Supporting information regarding the infections is available in the appendix. IQTV=Iquitos virus. MDDV=Madre de Dios virus. PDEV=Perdões virus.

Figure 5: Robustness of laboratory diagnosis of human infections with Oropouche virus and reassortants

(A) Predominance of serodiagnosis and viral isolation. (B) Widespread use of molecular detection and sequencing. For both panels, confirmed cases were detected with sequencing, RT-PCR, neutralisation tests, viral isolation combined with CF, or seroconversion in paired samples with any type of serological tool. Probable cases were detected with ELISA, immunofluorescence assays, or haemagglutination inhibition tests on a single sample. Studies with no black dots are based solely on symptoms. CF=complement fixation. *Studies include different study groups, presented separately. † Describes cases of Iquitos virus. # Describes cases of Madre de Dios virus. For clarity of presentation only one surname is shown. Details on the studies summarised are available in the appendix.

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